

The recovery in October 1778 of the skull of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni* Mantell, 1829 (Squamata, Mosasauridae; upper Maastrichtian, the Netherlands) – a reconstruction

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ABSTRACT

Ever since the first mention and illustration, in 1798, of what was to become the type specimen of the late Maastrichtian marine monitor lizard, *Mosasaurus hoffmanni*, three decades later, the tale of its discovery, recovery, preparation and conservation has fascinated scientists and the general public alike. After having been lifted from the subterranean galleries of the Sint-Pietersberg near Maastricht, the limestone block with the skull came into the possession of canon Godding, who owned part of the galleries. The account of events presented by Barthélemy Faujas de Saint Fond, the geologist who arrived in Maastricht in January 1795 to assist the French revolutionary troops in procuring collections, has lately proved to be severely embellished, if not to say, altogether false. In the present paper, two issues are addressed. The first revolves around the fact that Godding quite possibly had additional skeletal remains of the same individual of which the skull was recovered; unfortunately, these must be presumed lost. The second pertains to the method used in extracting the block containing the skull. On the basis of field-work, as well as literature and archive studies, into the manner of block extraction in the Sint-Pietersberg subterranean galleries, two scenarios for the discovery and lifting of this particular block are proposed. The second scenario, here favoured, assumes a situation where workers ('blokbrekers' in Dutch) would have come across skeletal remains in a horizontal plane by breaking loose the lower (bottom) side of a block which would then have revealed pieces of the skeleton on the surface thus created. Following this, these skeletal remains, including the skull, were disengaged by working around them and the block containing the skull subsequently lifted in its entirety.

Keywords Reptilia, type specimen, subterranean galleries, Sint-Pietersberg, Maastricht

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INTRODUCTION

The latter half of the eighteenth century witnessed the discovery in the subterranean galleries of the Sint-Pietersberg, south of the city of Maastricht (province of Limburg, the Netherlands), of two incomplete skulls of a marine reptile (Buc'hoz 1782, Faujas de Saint Fond 1798-1803, van Regteren Altena 1956, Bardet & Jagt 1996, Reumer 2024). The first specimen, encountered in 1764, came into the possession of Jean-Baptiste Drouin, a French lieutenant-general and local collector, two years later. In 1783 it was acquired for Teylers Museum (Haarlem, the Netherlands), by Martinus van Marum, the museum's first director, where it is still on display (van Marum 1790). The second individual, recovered in October 1778 (Anonymous 1779), was to become the type specimen of the first-named mosasaurid lizard, *Mosasaurus hoffmanni* (Fig. 1). The account given by Faujas de Saint Fond of the seizure of the skull from Godding and the 'compensation' received by him, has on several occasions been shown to be false (Cremers 1942, Rompen 1995, Bardet & Jagt 1996, Pieters *et al.* 2012, 2019, Reumer 2024).

Both specimens originate from the higher portion of a lithostratigraphical unit that is currently referred to as the Nekum Member of the Maastricht Formation, although detailed data for the Teylers Museum individual (registration number TM F-07424) are lacking. In view of the fact that in the late 1990s (see Bardet & Jagt 1996) a study of a small matrix sample from the block preserving the type specimen of *M. hoffmanni* (registration number MNHN AC 9648) could be conducted (P.J. Felder & Jagt 1998), data on its provenance are precise; it stems from below the Kanne Horizon in the upper portion of the Nekum Member. The Kanne Horizon has recently been dated as 66.25 Ma by Vellekoop *et al.* (2022, see also Keutgen 2018).

The Sint-Pietersberg and its wider surroundings constitute the type area of the Maastrichtian Stage in its current definition, dated as 72.10 to 66.04 million years (www.stratigraphy.org). Generally speaking, the type section is considered to be the steep rock face below the Lichtenberg farmstead, close to where Dumont (1849) originally defined his 'système maestrichtien'. Current outcrops in the former ENCI-Heidelberg-Cement Group quarry allow access to most of the Gulpen Formation (Lixhe 1-3 and Lanaye members), comprising white or greyish, soft, fine-grained limestones interspersed with continuous flint levels and most of the overlying Maastricht Formation, which consists of yellowish soft and fine- to coarse-grained limestones with discontinuous flint levels or nodules (W.M. Felder & Bosch 1998, 2000, Jagt & Jagt-Yazykova 2012, Vellekoop *et al.* 2022).

In general, the Maastrichtian type area may be considered the cradle of research related to mosasauroid reptiles, since the first documented remains of these animals were discovered in the subterranean galleries of the Sint-Pietersberg in the latter half of the eighteenth century, and this remained the main source of material until limestone quarrying in opencast pits became the norm (see e.g. Cuvier 1808, Dollo 1882, Ubaghs 1897, Bardet & Jagt 1996, Bardet 2012, Hovens 2020a, Jagt *et al.* 2024a). Naturally, this has resulted in the find of additional mosasaur specimens, of various species, some even new to science (Dortangs *et al.* 2002, Bastiaans *et al.* 2020, Barten *et al.* 2026). Alongside, research of archived documents has continued unabated, and this has yielded novel data for two issues that are addressed in the present paper.

The first pertains to the fact that additional skeletal remains belonging to the famous skull must have been in Godding's possession since they appear in an inventory of his legacy, but must now be presumed lost. The other issue revolves around

Figure 1 Artist's impression of the recovery of what was to become the type specimen of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni* Mantell, 1829 from the subterranean galleries of Sint-Pietersberg (Maastricht), as supplied by Faujas de Saint Fond (1798-1803) (Wikipedia). Note that this is depicted as a mirror image, as can be judged from the skull itself (MNHN AC 9648), on display at the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris).

Figure 2 Excerpt of the inventory of Godding’s worldly goods, drawn up in French after his death. Translated into English, the text reads as follows, ‘Beside the staircase down into the wine cellar of dean Godding’s house, located near the church of Saint Servatius in Maastricht, stood two cases with pieces of a petrified crocodile [‘deux caisses avec des fragments d’un crocodile pétrifié’]. Source: Historisch Centrum Limburg, Maastricht. Notarissen ter standplaats Maastricht, 1544-1842 [20.241], inventory number 4112).

Figure 3 Detail (left) of the ‘Carte du plateau de St. Pierre levée à vue et dessinée par Mr. Bory de St. Vincent’ (1821), the yellow rectangle indicating the residence ‘Maaszig’ (with, as the name suggests, a view over the River Maas [Meuse]). The red rectangle (= see detail at right) indicates the former possession of dean Godding and its vicinity, between the River Jeker (‘Jaar’) and the fortress of Sint-Pieter. The red arrow points at the residence itself, the green rectangle marks the ‘large entrance’ (oblique letter A), the blue indicating the small entrance (letter B). Source: Historisch Centrum Limburg, Maastricht, Collection RAL, inventory number 246.

the extraction method used in lifting the block containing the skull, because it has recently been pointed out that this block does not reveal any traces left by saws and/or chisels, and all skull bones are undamaged (i.e. not sawn into) which would imply lifting of the block in its entirety (Jagt et al. 2024b). Two scenarios are here proposed, based on the method of block extraction in the Sint-Pietersberg galleries.

A CLERGYMAN’S COLLECTION

An inventory of canon Joannes Theodorus Godding’s (1721-1797) possessions, drawn up after his death, contains an interesting item referred to as ‘Des fragments d’un crocodile pétrifié’ (Fig. 2).

Godding was the first owner of the then already famous skull, which had caused quite a stir in revolutionary France. It took

only two months after the seizure of the city of Maastricht by the revolutionary troops in November 1794 for this important object of natural history to be put on transport to Paris where it arrived early in 1795 (Rompen 1995, Bardet & Jagt 1996, Bardet 2012, Hovens 2020a). It was Homburg (2015) who, at long last, settled the question as to the exact date of the find of this ‘trophée de guerre’: October 1778 (compare Anonymous 1779). For a long time it was assumed that the fossil had been discovered underneath the ‘Maaszig’ residence (Hovens 2020b), near the River Maas (Meuse), which was held to be Godding’s country house, who resided at the Servatius chapter in Maastricht. However, it has subsequently turned out that Godding’s country house was not Maaszig, but a residence along the road to the Belgian village of Kanne, situated near the River Jeker, a tributary of the River Maas, and close to ‘La

Figure 4 Pierre-Joseph Buc'hoz (1782) presented this (mirror-imaged) drawing of the mosasaur skull recovered from a subterranean gallery of the Sint-Pietersberg in October 1778. As far as we are aware this is the first-ever illustration of the skull. Source: Koninklijke Bibliotheek, 's-Gravenhage.

Grande Entrée' (large entrance) to the Sint-Pietersberg galleries (Fig. 3, Hovens 2020b). This 'grande entrée' collapsed in 1916 (see Ogg 2016, Ogg et al., 2024 (https://nl.wikipedia.org/wiki/Noordelijk_Gangstelsel, <https://mestreechtersteerke.nl/pag-lagrandentree.htm>)).

It is assumed here that the mosasaur skull was discovered near the large entrance, but it cannot be ruled out entirely that it was found further away down the subterranean galleries in the Sint-Pietersberg, part of which was owned by Godding. Soon after the lifting and transport of the block preserving the skull, the canon put it on display, either in a showcase at his country house or somewhere in the adjoining subterranean gallery. One of the scientists who paid Godding a visit in his country house was the famous naturalist Petrus Camper (see Camper 1786, van Regteren Altena 1956, Hovens 2020a).

The item in the listing of Godding's possessions, drawn up after his death in 1797, referred to above, is of special note. It makes reference to two cases with fragments of a 'petrified crocodile' (Fig. 2). These cases appeared to have been placed next to the stairs leading down into the wine cellar at Godding's residence in the city centre, close to the church of Saint Servatius (Vrijthof, Maastricht city centre). At the time, what would later become the first mosasaur to be formally described was often likened to a huge crocodile skull, for instance by Faujas de Saint Fond (1798-1803), in reference to Godding's treasure. Therefore, the mention of fragments of

a 'petrified crocodile' as part of Godding's legacy, deserves attention.

In 1815 Catharina Godding-Soiron (1751-1819), widow of a nephew of canon Godding, did her best to regain the skull from the French government, or at least to receive retribution for the loss of the then already famous fossil. In her request she writes (see Hovens 2020a), 'j'ai encore en ma possession deux parties laterales de ce crocodile, qui reunies avec le principal morceau qui est à Paris, complettent cette interessante petrification'. Catharina did not succeed. A second attempt in 1823 by her sister-in-law, Rosa Godding, also failed (see Ubachs 1969).

The communication that two 'lateral parts' would 'complete the principal piece' is intriguing, to say the least and raises several questions. Firstly, what does 'to complete' mean? Pieces that would complete the skull, or pieces that would make the skeleton as a whole more complete, possibly referring to shoulder blades? When Petrus Camper visited Godding in his country house in 1782, he noted in his diary not only the skull, but also shoulder blades preserved in a piece of rock ('een stuk steen waar in schouderbladen ...') (see also Camper 1786, compare van Regteren Altena 1956). These shoulder blades may well refer to the 'lateral pieces' mentioned by Catharina Godding-Soiron. If these pieces were kept in two cases, this would imply that the limestone block that held the shoulder blades had been broken into two between 1782 and 1797.

Secondly, was the widow Godding certain in claiming that the skull and lateral pieces belonged to one and the same individual, or was this merely conjecture? Without further evidence we cannot prove that the skull and lateral pieces were found in close association, having originated in a single skeleton. Seen in that light a remark by Pierre-Joseph Buc'hoz in his *'Dons merveilleux'* (1782) is of note. He mentioned a 'tête pétrifiée d'un animal inconnu, trouvé dans les carrières de la montagne Saint-Pierre près de Maestricht, de 3 pieds de largeur sur 16 pouces de hauteur, déposée dans le cabinet de M. le doyen des chanoines de cette ville [= Godding]' (compare Fig. 4). In this instance, the word 'trouvé' refers to 'animal' (masculine in French) and not to 'tête' (feminine in French), while the word 'déposée' obviously refers to the skull.

From the above, it may be concluded that the fragments mentioned in Godding's inventory (Fig. 2) were not crocodylian in nature, but in fact did belong to a mosasaur, and more than likely to what was to become the type specimen of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni*. It is well conceivable that Godding put only the spectacular skull on display, and that the less attractive pieces were kept separate in one or more cases.

The question as to why, and since when, these fragments were boxed up at Godding's house in the city centre and not in his residence at Sint-Pieter cannot be answered at the moment. Nor do we know whether or not the scientific commission, led by Faujas de Saint Fond, that accompanied the French revolutionary army in their quest for and seizure of the skull was aware of the other skeletal fragments ('lateral pieces').

Moreover, whatever happened to (the content of) these two cases? The auction papers listing Godding's inventory on April 24 to 28 of the year 1797 (or 5-9 floréal an 5, in the French revolutionary calendar) make no mention of these. Probably, they remained with Godding's family members, which also explains why Catharina Godding-Soiron could refer to the two lateral parts that she owned as belonging to the 'crocodile' that had been looted in 1794 and sent to Paris the following year.

From about 1820 onwards, there is no more mention of those 'lateral pieces' in written sources (literature and archives) known to us. For now, they are presumed lost.

LEVEL OF PROVENANCE DETERMINED

On the basis of a bioclast analysis of a small piece of matrix from the block preserving the type specimen of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni*, P.J. Felder & Jagt (1998) were able to determine that this must have originated from just below the so-called Kanne Horizon (Fig. 5), a condensed and winnowed level that is particularly rich in test fragments of the echinoid *Hemipneustes striatoradiatus* (Leske, 1778). Thus, Bardet & Jagt's (1996) observation was substantiated.

To date, the range of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni* in the type area of the Maastrichtian Stage is fairly well known (Jagt *et al.* 1995, Kuypers *et al.* 1998, Mulder *et al.* 1998, Mulder 1999, 2003, Jagt 2005, Cornelissen *et al.* 2012, Barten *et al.* 2026). The first representatives have been recorded from the lower Lanaye Member (Gulpen Formation). The taxon ranges to within a metre below the Cretaceous-Paleogene (K/Pg)

Figure 5 Log of the Nekum Member (Maastricht Formation), with indication of horizons and levels of fossil hash and flint nodules (modified from W.M. Felder & Bosch, 1998, see also W.M. Felder & Bosch, 2000). The arrow denotes the level of provenance of the type specimen of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni*, as determined by Bardet & Jagt (1996) and P.J. Felder & Jagt (1998).

boundary in the region, which equates with the Berg en Terblijt Horizon in the upper Meerssen Member (Maastricht Formation, Jagt *et al.* 2008). This implies a stratigraphical range of around 1.75 million years, following data supplied by Keutgen (2018) and Vellekoop *et al.* (2022).

The skeletal anatomy of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni* has also been recorded in detail, the most important contributions being those of Dollo (1882) [who also described the co-occurring plioplatecarpine mosasaur *Plioplatecarpus marshi* Dollo, 1882 (see Lingham-Soliar, 1994)], Lingham-Soliar (1995), Grigoriev (2014) and Street & Caldwell (2017).

Both in the Lanaye Member (Gulpen Formation) and Nekum Member (Maastricht Formation), *Mosasaurus hoffmanni* co-occurs with '*Prognathodon*' *saturator* Dortangs, Schulp, Mulder, Jagt, Peeters & De Graaf 2002, the latter record being based on material described by Ubaghs (1879), as document-

ed by Schulp *et al.* (2013), Recently, Mohr (2024) has provided convincing arguments in favour of considering the genus *Prognathodon* Dollo, 1889 to be monotypical (type species: *Prognathodon solvayi* Dollo, 1889) (compare Lingham-Soliar & Nolf 1990). All other taxa referred to this genus would need to be transferred to other genera.

THE RECOVERY ITSELF – TWO SCENARIOS

The Sint-Pietersberg is well known for the extraction of limestone, to be used as building stones, in subterranean quarries (galleries), over a continuous period from at least the 13th century until the first half of the 20th. In these underground quarries, work was carried out according to the principle of 'rooms and pillars', with the word rooms referring to the galleries themselves, or the open volume created by the extraction of limestone. The word pillars refers to the rocks remaining that support the topsoil and prevent collapse.

The height of the galleries may vary amongst quarries or parts of quarries, with a minimum of 1,5 metres and a maximum of 12 metres. The height of the gallery, or more specifically the level at which the stone was quarried in the bedrock, is largely determined by laterally occurring geological phenomena. Most important are the quality of limestone for use as a building stone and the presence (in terms of building stone extraction) of contaminants such as hardgrounds, fossil hash levels and flint nodules. In the Sint-Pietersberg, the Nekum Member (Maastricht Formation) constitutes the prime level extracted for use as building stones (Kisters *et al.* 2015, W.M. Felder & Bosch 2000, Lahaye *et al.* 2022) and the main source of skeletal finds of mosasaurs.

In the former quarry now referred to as the 'Noordelijk gangenstelsel', the limestone of this unit was extracted over a height of about 7 metres. The ceiling of the galleries is situated just below a hardground, at the level of the Caster Horizon (Fig. 5), while the floor sits above a level with relatively abundant, scattered flint nodules, nearer to the base of the member (Fig. 5, compare W.M. Felder & Bosch 1998, 2000). In between, the limestone is not entirely homogeneous. Difficult levels encountered during quarrying included a mostly 10- to 20-cm-thick, fossil-rich bed, situated above the Kanne Horizon (Fig. 5) and, occurring locally, levels of up to 1 metre in thickness, with relatively numerous, scattered flint nodules.

The subterranean quarries of the Sint-Pietersberg have been active over a period of about 700 years, and during this time various methods of extracting stones, with a variety of tools and ways to extract blocks from the bedrock are seen. However, the basic principle has always remained the same. The main feature of extraction for the purpose of obtaining building stone is the quarrying of block-shaped stone. Primary tools included specific types of (wide-toothed) saws and chisels, which were used to make cuts and rectangular slots in the bedrock, the marks of which are still visible on the walls and ceilings in the underground quarries. The size of the blocks depends, among other things, on the distance between these cuts and slots. By studying the marks left by these tools, it is possible to reconstruct the successive steps in the process of extracting blocks. Caris (1996) reconstructed the method used in most of the former underground quarry of

the 'Noordelijk gangenstelsel' and described this in detail.

In order to quarry the entire level with usable stone over the full height, work was carried out according to a method in which two types of work can be distinguished: firstly, to extend the gallery in the bedrock at the level of the ceiling (roof) and, secondly, the deepening of the floor. Gallery extension started at the ceiling; the result of this work was a gallery of about 3 metres in width and about 1,5 to 3 metres in height, between the Caster and Kanne horizons (Fig. 5) (Caris 1996, Amendt 2009). Following this the floor is deepened; two variants may be distinguished. In the first variant, the entire level that is suitable for building stone was quarried at once, by immediately deepening the floor of the gallery at ceiling level to its maximum depth. In the second variant, only the gallery at the ceiling level was initially made, after which deepening of the floor took place in later periods and in one or more phases (Caris 2006, Amendt 2009).

This knowledge of quarrying methods may provide insight into the situation in which the mosasaur skull was found in October 1778 by 'blokkbrekers', who were engaged in quarrying the stone, in that part of the underground quarries of the Sint-Pietersberg now referred to as the 'Noordelijk gangenstelsel'. Now that the exact stratigraphical provenance of the type specimen of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni*, i.e., from just below the Kanne Horizon within the upper Nekum Member (Fig. 5, compare Bardet & Jagt 1996, P.J. Felder & Jagt 1998) has been established, we may conclude that these skeletal remains were found during deepening of the floor. In the 'Noordelijk gangenstelsel' work was carried out along the principle of deepening the total usable height with usable stone in several stages (van Schaik 1938, Caris 2006, Amendt & Jennekens 2019, Ogg *et al.* 2024).

The process of deepening a gallery in several stages may be described as layer-by-layer extraction. Each stage involves the extraction of a layer deeper into the floor, with the gallery at the work site often taking the form of a staircase, where the different floor levels can be regarded as 'steps'. The height and length of such steps vary and depend on the height of the block and the progress per step, respectively. Mainly saws and chisels were used to make the necessary cuts and rectangular slots that give the stone its blocky shape (Fig. 6). The bottom side of the block is broken loose from the bedrock by hammering in a wedge at the bottom of the block. When the block is removed, a new piece of floor is created on this 'step', which in turn can be deepened in the same way. It is during these works that, at some point, one of the 'blokkbrekers' must have observed fossil remains that led to the discovery of the mosasaur skull.

Based on the description above, it is possible to come up with two possible scenarios with regard to the discovery and lifting of the mosasaur skull in 1778. Firstly, the skeletal remains became visible by exposure in a vertical plane, when cuts and slots were made and, secondly, the remains were exposed in a horizontal plane, namely that at which the block was broken loose by the workmen. The first scenario assumes a situation where the workers found skeletal remains in a vertical plane and recognised them as such. The vertical plane is created by making a saw cut or cut slot and, during this

Figure 6A, B Twentieth-century photographs offering an impression of block extraction while deepening of the floor, a method also used in the 'Noordelijk gangenstelsel'. **A** This is the so-called 'Kannermethode' (Breuls, 1985), a specific working method used in the 19th and 20th centuries in subterranean galleries near the village of Kanne (Belgium). Three floor levels are visible, in the middle one, a block is cut out and broken loose at the bottom (photograph: Sjeng Simons Collection). **B** While deepening the floor, the working site takes the form of a staircase, in which the different floor levels can be regarded as 'steps'. This allowed the workers to extract blocks of limestone over the entire level suitable for building stone. This particular gallery was located in the so-called 'Zak van Francken' section of the Sint-Pietersberg, it no longer exists, having been quarried away by the cement industry (photograph by Hans Kamphoven, John Hageman Collection).

process, a cross section of fossil remains would have become visible. In view of the fact that no traces of tools are seen in the block preserving the type specimen, the adjacent limestone must have been screened by the workmen for additional bones. In the course of this, the skull was encountered and recovered in its entirety.

The second scenario assumes a situation where the workers came across skeletal remains in a horizontal plane and recognised them as such. The horizontal plane was created by breaking loose the lower (bottom) side of a block and this would have revealed a piece of the specimen on the surface thus created. Following this, the skeletal remains were worked out very carefully, and the block with the skull disengaged and lifted in its entirety.

When both scenarios are assessed in relation to the working methods used and the condition, shape and size of the block containing the type specimen, scenario 2 appears to be the most plausible. It is not known to what extent workers at the time were skilled in recognising fossil remains. The first scenario requires a relatively advanced level of knowledge in order

to recognise a cross section of brown-coloured fossil bone, to find the skull within close proximity and to recover it intact. The second scenario fits the principle of deepening the floor well, where blocks were broken loose from the bedrock at various heights. When some of the skeletal remains became exposed after breaking loose a block, they must have been identifiable even when workmen were not particularly versed in recognising fossils and it must have proved possible to clear the entire top of the skull further. This may explain why there are no traces of tools visible that would have damaged the bones and why the skull, which exceeds the size of a commonly extracted block, was not cut by saws. Scenario 2 is also in line with the image presented by Faujas de Saint Fond (1798-1803) of the transport of the skull, in a block measuring in excess of a metre, from the subterranean gallery (see Fig. 1), although it is not known whether this represents a reliable representation of what went on. It should also be noted that the top of the skull is shown as already completely prepared free from the limestone matrix.

Figure 7 Schematic representation of a gallery located in the subterranean quarry 'Zonneberg gangenstelsel', which originally formed part of the 'Noordelijk gangenstelsel'. The layer-by-layer extraction method and the staircase-shaped working site are clearly visible here. The section shows the eight different floor levels (numbered 1 to 8) in their current state, whereas the dotted lines represent the original floor level before it was covered by waste materials from the stone extraction process. In the illustrated case, both the gallery at ceiling level (1) and the first stage of floor deepening (2) are located between the Caster Horizon (sitting just above the ceiling) and a fossil-rich bed located directly above the Kanne Horizon (zone A). Initially, the gallery floor was deepened down to level 6, which lies above a zone with scattered and relatively numerous flint nodules (Zone B). In a later period, levels 7 and 8 were deepened in several stages down to the lowest floor level (drawing by Kevin Amendt and Chiara Caravello, 2025, the top view being based on the 1942 map of David C. van Schaik. Cross-section measurements were taken by Kevin Amendt in 2009).

CONCLUSIONS

The find in subterranean galleries of the Sint-Pietersberg (Maastricht) of the second mosasaur skull in October 1778, the later type specimen of *Mosasaurus hoffmanni*, has fascinated scientists and the general public alike and still does so today. Novel aspects of its discovery and recovery, gleaned mostly from archive research, suggest that canon Godding quite possibly had additional skeletal remains of the same individual of which the skull was recovered and also allows the way of extraction of the block with the skull to be reconstructed. It is believed that workers would have come across skeletal remains, maybe of the postcranial skeleton, in a horizontal plane by breaking loose the lower (bottom) side of a block which would then have revealed a piece of the skull on the surface thus created. Subsequently, the skull was disengaged by working around it and then lifted and transported out of the gallery in its entirety. The absence of any traces of saws and chisels and the sheer size of the block with the intact skull would favour this interpretation.

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